

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR AMONG TEACHERS IN SCHOOLS OF TIRUCHIRAPALLI DISTRICT

S. RALIYA BEGUM

Research Scholar, Department of Management, Jamal Institute of Management, Jamal Mohamed College, Trichy.

Dr. M. A. SHAKILA BANU

Associate Professor, Department of Management, Jamal Institute of Management, Jamal Mohamed College Trichy.

Abstract

Teachers are the backbone of our country. Teachers have a critical role in the development of students' knowledge and abilities. The purpose of this study is to look into the organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction of school teachers. For the purpose of this study, 377 respondents from various schools in Tiruchirappalli took part. The information gathered was evaluated using descriptive statistics in SPSS version 16. When the organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction levels of school teachers were compared, it was discovered that there was no significant difference in their levels of satisfaction, regardless of gender.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, School Teachers, Students.

INTRODUCTION

Teacher's roles in society and education may shift throughout time, but their importance remains constant. Educating institutions face a significant difficulty in attracting and retaining qualified teachers. A cheerful attitude is a vital trait of a teacher in education. To be satisfied with their profession, every teacher must have the ability and clear intention to carry out their responsibilities with maximum dedication. The connection between job satisfaction and OCB has been analyzed in a number of studies. Job satisfaction refers to a person's emotional and psychological reactions to their work. Job satisfaction is defined as the link between what people expect and what they get. Without satisfaction, no work can be done efficiently. Teachers play a vital role in the development of the nation and its future people.

Only few studies have analyzed the impact of job satisfaction on various dimensions of OCB in Indian educational institutions, so it needs further analysis. As a result, job satisfaction is an important term that is vital not only to an individual but also to the wellbeing of society. Job satisfaction is one aspect that contributes to classroom performance and school productivity. When teachers are happy in their employment, they are more motivated to teach their students efficiently. Other countries around the world, like India, are attempting to improve their educational quality in order to satisfy the demands of globalisation.

Only if teachers are happy in their employment will they work to their full potential. Only few studies have analyzed the impact of job satisfaction on various dimensions of OCB in Indian educational institutions, so it needs further analysis. As a result, job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior is a significant phenomenon in every industry, particularly in the teaching profession.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

One of the most commonly studied topics is job satisfaction. Job satisfaction serves as a moderator in the development of the link between working conditions and individual results. (2001, Dorman and Zapf)

Ahmed, Raheem, and Jamal (2003) studied the job satisfaction of 236 secondary school teachers. When comparing male and female teachers, it was discovered that female teachers are more contented. Teachers in government schools reported higher levels of satisfaction than those in private institutions. A study on job satisfaction was undertaken by Gupta and Sahu (2009). It examines the relationship between job happiness and organizational stress, as well as the position of control held by vocational teachers. The findings demonstrated that organizational stress and place of control on vocational school are not significantly different by gender.

Noll (2004) investigated the elements that influence teacher work satisfaction. Teachers' job happiness is influenced by motivation, their relationship with the administration, and their working environment, according to the findings. Agarwal (2004) conducted research on primary and secondary school teachers' job satisfaction. According to the findings, government school instructors who are experienced and married are more satisfied than private school teachers. It was also discovered that age and marital status have no bearing on job satisfaction.

The survey was performed by R.D.Sharma and Jeevan Jyoti (2006) among private and government school teachers in Jammu city, with a sample size of 120 instructors. Teachers' satisfaction is low, according to the report, while private school teachers are more satisfied than government teachers. Muchhal and Satish (2010) did a study on elementary school teachers' job satisfaction in Bagpat district. According to the findings, there is a difference between female and male teachers.

Teachers' satisfaction levels and attitudes toward teaching are influenced by their gender, marital status, and minimum qualification, according to Kumar and Bhatiya (2011).

A survey of teacher work satisfaction was done by John (2010), Mehta (2012), and Zilli (2012) to see if the type of organization affected the teacher's view. According to the findings, there is a considerable disparity in teacher satisfaction between public and private schools.

Iqbar and Akhtar (2012) did a study to examine the satisfaction levels of male and female public school secondary school teachers in Pakistan and the Lahore district. The T test can be used to compare satisfaction levels. The results revealed that female teachers are more satisfied than male teachers.

Raj and Lalitha (2013) performed a survey on teacher job satisfaction in both private and public schools. The findings revealed that there is no substantial difference in teacher satisfaction between private and public schools.

Moorthy (2013) carried out an empirical study to determine the level of satisfaction among female employees. The outcome revealed that the level of satisfaction is modest.

Achanta and Reddy (2014) performed a survey of primary school teachers' satisfaction levels.

Organ (1990) examined OCB and the mutual trust that underlies social exchange relationships ensures that OCB will be reflected in the long run.

Lester and Brower (2003) researched that employees' perceptions of their leaders' trust in them influenced their work performance and OCB.

Findings of Tyler and Blader (2003) and Gould-Williams (2003) reported that job satisfaction simultaneously influences organizational citizenship behaviors.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Teachers' involvement and commitment are entirely dependent on morale, motivation, job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior. Motivation, organizational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction are important in all organizations, including schools. Teachers are the key players in educational institutions who ensure that the organization's goals and objectives are met, and they are the key people who mold students to excel in their careers. A survey on teacher job satisfaction was conducted in 12 countries, revealing that teachers are dissatisfied with their jobs. Absenteeism, irregularity, and a lack of commitment have all been identified as consequences of low job satisfaction (Bennell & Akyeampong, 2007). Teacher job satisfaction is important not only for teachers but also for students. Job satisfaction can predict teacher retention and commitment (Shann 2001).

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to compare job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior among teachers at schools. The importance of teachers in our culture cannot be overstated. The quality of education is directly proportional to the quality of teachers. The future of the pupils is designed by the teachers. A teacher who enjoys their job is more likely to work well and efficiently. If instructors are under stress, they will be dissatisfied with their jobs and have a bad attitude about them. As a result, it is vital to determine the factors that influence teachers' job satisfaction. Teachers may work marvels in changing students' raw ingredients into wonderful end products, such as whole people and responsible citizens.

When teachers are happy with their work, they might generate more energy. Chen (2010) conducted a study on teacher job satisfaction. The findings revealed that there is no significant gender difference in mean score among teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To determine the level of teacher satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior in schools.
- To compare school teachers' organizational citizenship behavior with respect to their school administration.
- To compare school teachers' job satisfaction with respect to their school administration.
- To conduct a comparison study between teachers' organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H1: There is no substantial difference in job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior between teachers in schools.

H2: There is no substantial difference in job satisfaction organizational citizenship behavior between teachers in schools.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The current research is a descriptive study. The primary goal of this research is to examine the levels of satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior among teachers in schools. The results of primary data are used to carry out the same. The primary data was collected with a self-structured questionnaire. The survey used a five-point likert scale that ranged from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The questionnaire was divided into three sections. The first section dealt with the demographic profile of respondents, while the second portion focused on aspects linked to job satisfaction and the third section deals with OCB.

Sample Design

Teachers are from various schools in Trichy district served as the sampling unit for this study. The sample size was chosen to represent the entire population while also providing a realistic image. The sample size was 377 in total. The samples were taken using the random sampling method. Out of 400 samples, 377 samples were chosen from various schools in Tiruchirappalli district.

Tree Structured Analysis for Job Satisfaction of Teachers

Table 1: Model Summary of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour of Teachers

Specifications	Growing Method	CHAID
	Dependent Variable	Job Satisfaction
	Independent Variables	Conscientiousness, Sportsmanship, Civic Virtue, Courtesy, Altruism
	Validation	None
	Maximum Tree Depth	3
	Minimum Cases in Parent Node	100
	Minimum Cases in Child Node	50
Results	Independent Variables Included	D1
	Number of Nodes	4
	Number of Terminal Nodes	3
	Depth	1

Table 2: Risk of the Model for Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour of Teachers

Risk	
Estimate	Std. Error
.667	.065
Growing Method: CHAID Dependent Variable: JS	

Table 3: Gain Summary for Nodes for Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour of Teachers

Gain Summary for Nodes			
Node	N	Percent	Mean
3	51	13.5%	4.20
2	270	71.6%	3.87
1	56	14.9%	2.96
Growing Method: CHAID Dependent Variable: JS			

CHART 1:

Tree Diagram for the Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour of Teachers

From the tree analysis model summary, it is clear that the organizational citizenship behavior occurs in organizations is important independent variables. This variable is contributing more towards job satisfaction of teachers. Indeed, organizational citizenship behavior occurs in organization is important independent variables that have created adequate towards job satisfaction.

Friedman Test for Significant Difference between Mean Ranks of Gender of the Teachers and Organizational citizenship Behavior

Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between mean ranks towards organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between mean ranks towards organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction.

Table 4: Friedman Test for Significant Difference between Mean Ranks towards Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job Satisfaction

Variables	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Degree of freedom	Assumption significant
Conscientiousness	3.83	74.504	5	.000
Sportsmanship	3.22			
Civic Virtue	3.36			
Courtesy	3.19			
Altruism	3.80			
Job Satisfaction	3.59			

From the above table, it is found out that all the variables related to the organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction of teachers had significant values less than 0.05 at 1 Per cent significance; thus the null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is significant difference between mean ranks towards organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction of teachers. Out of seventy two organizational citizenship behavior and job satisfaction of teachers variables, “Conscientiousness” has the highest rank (3.83). So, organizational citizenship behavior opinion towards teachers is influenced by job satisfaction among teachers. Main reason for this is that the job satisfaction among teachers reach at large extent.

ANOVA Test for Gender of the Teachers Job Satisfaction and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

variables	F-Value	Significant Value	Result
Job Satisfaction	4.713	.010	Not significant
Conscientiousness	1.887	.153	Not significant
Sportsmanship	.418	.659	Not significant
Civic Virtue	3.198	.042	Not significant
Courtesy	3.762	.024	Not significant
Altruism	3.568	.029	Not significant

There is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the teachers and job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the mean score of Gender of the teachers and job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior. The main reason for this is that the gender of the teachers does not take any role in job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior. Here, the teachers do not have any idea about organizational citizenship behavior irrespective of their gender.

LIMITATIONS

The current study is based on data collected in the Trichy district. Some of the responses from respondents may be skewed, and it uses questionnaires as the primary way of gathering information, which has certain drawbacks.

CONCLUSION

According to the findings of this study, there is no significant difference in job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior between school teachers, and there is also no significant difference in job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behavior between school teachers based on gender. As a result, the study shows that providing Organizational support to teachers in order to improve job satisfaction is critical. Teachers' job satisfaction should be improved in whatever way possible. As a result of this study's findings that independence at work is the most desired feature of job satisfaction, schools should establish self-motivated teams. Self-development opportunities, short-term training, and seminars are some tips for achieving job satisfaction.

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